

Nanometer-nanosecond dynamics in laser-induced expansion/contraction and ablation of polymer films[†]

Takuji Tada^a and Hiroshi Masuhara^{b,c*}

^aSD1, Equipment Development Division, Medical Systems Research & Development Center, Research & Development Management Headquarters, FUJIFILM Corporation, 798 Miyanodai, Kaisei-machi, Ashigarakamigun, Kanagawa 258-8538, Japan

^bDepartment of Applied Chemistry and Institute of Molecular Science, National Chiao Tung University, 1001, Ta Hshueh Rd., Hsinchu 30010, Taiwan

^cGraduate School of Materials Science, Nara Institute of Science and Technology, Takayama 8916-5, Ikoma, Nara 630-0192, Japan

E-mail : masuhara@masuhara.jp, takuji_tada@fujifilm.co.jp

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Abstract : In this account we have summarized our systematic studies on laser ablation and related phenomena of polymer films by utilizing time-resolved absorption spectroscopy and nanosecond interferometry. Polystyrene, poly(methyl methacrylate), poly(methyl acrylate), azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer, nitrocellulose, triazene polymer, polyurethane, and polyimide were examined, and their expansion and contraction dynamics were confirmed directly at the laser fluence below the ablation threshold. The molecular species which are formed by intense laser excitation are identified by absorption spectroscopy and correlated to the morphological changes. We proposed the cyclic multiphotonic absorption mechanism and explained well the ablation and related phenomena in terms of photophysics and photochemistry.

Keywords : Polymer film, laser, dynamics, nanosecond.

Introduction

Polymer films have received much attention as interesting materials for laser-processing, because their optical, physical, and chemical properties can be controlled by introducing appropriate substituents or doping the functional molecules in the films. Fluorine-substituted polymer film has been applied as a resist material for producing the integrated circuit of semiconductor and the spatial resolution of fabricated pattern is approaching to less than several tens nm. Refractive index and morphological changes of the azobenzene-substituted polymer are induced by laser irradiation, which is expected to be useful for making high-density memory and optical wave guide¹. Bonding between polymer microparticle and polymer film doped with Rhodamine-B is realized by laser irradiation²

and this bonding technique is applied to fabrication of highly integrated protein chip³. These are only some examples among tremendous amount of reports on laser-processing of polymeric materials.

For further progress in the laser-processing, it is important and indispensable to understand dynamics and mechanism underlying laser-induced morphological change of polymer film. Short pulse laser irradiation generates high-densely excited states of chromophores doped or bonded in/to polymer, and their successive relaxation through various photophysical and photochemical processes eventually leads to the morphological change of the polymer film. Therefore, time-resolved imaging and spectroscopic studies have been conducted to bridge a gap in understanding between molecular photochemical

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

reactions and macroscopic morphological changes³⁻²⁷. Namely, combination of time-resolved imaging and spectroscopy enables us to interpret dynamics of macroscopic change in viewpoint of the excited state behavior of molecules and to understand how electronic excitation evolves to morphological changes.

Importance of time-resolved studies on laser ablation mechanism :

Etching of a polymer film surface by high-intensity laser pulse was first reported by Namba *et al.* for poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA)²⁸ and by Srinivasan *et al.* for poly(ethylene terephthalate)²⁹. This phenomenon was called laser ablation and its mechanism has received much attention from many chemists, physicists, and electronics engineers. Srinivasan *et al.* and Stuke *et al.* investigated laser ablation dynamics of many kinds of polymer films^{12,29-31}. Pettit and Sauerbrey and co-workers have been investigated the ablation dynamics of polyimide film^{32,33}. Dyer and co-workers studied laser ablation dynamics of polymer films, particularly its incubation effect³⁴. Fotakis and co-workers made clear photochemical and photophysical effects on UV ablation of polymers doped with photosensitive molecules³⁵. Dlott *et al.* clarified energy re-distribution dynamics and chemical reaction mechanisms of doped polymer film after pulsed laser irradiation⁹. Lippert and co-workers focused their attention to ablation dynamics of photosensitive polymers^{26,27}. Moreover, modeling and numerical study on laser ablation have been conducted by Garrison and co-workers, who extended computational simulation of fragmentation dynamics of excited molecules³⁶. Arnold and co-workers studied the laser ablation dynamics on the basis of numerical analysis of kinetic models³⁷.

Historically, the following two mechanisms have been discussed. One is photothermal mechanism, in which absorbed photon energy is converted to heat by intramolecular and lattice vibrational relaxation, heating up materials, and then thermal decomposition occurs. Another is photochemical mechanism, in which electronically excited polymer directly decomposes to gaseous small molecules, which exerts high pressure in the film and induces fragmentation, leading to the etching of the film surface. In both cases formation and deactivation reactions of transient species, such as excited molecules, radicals, and decomposed molecules, are important to dis-

uss the mechanisms. It is necessary and indispensable to elucidate the behavior of transient species by direct measurement with time-resolved spectroscopy.

Spectroscopic measurements :

The time-resolved reflectivity of ArF excimer laser-irradiated polyimide film has been investigated by Pettit and co-workers and they showed that the dynamics reflectivity is at least partially due to optical changes in the solid polymer³². Yabe and co-workers studied the laser ablation of benzyl or pyrene-doped PMMA film and explained fluence dependence of etch depth by considering absorbance change owing to photolysis and generation of excited state of the dopant⁸. Dlott *et al.* reported that photon energy absorbed by doped molecule was converted to heat through vibrational cooling and heat up the polymer matrix through multiphonon up-pumping, which was elucidated by utilizing time-resolved Raman spectroscopy⁹. They also reported that thermal equilibrium between doped and excited molecule and non-excited polymer matrix was achieved in the 100 ps time scale. Laser ablation dynamics of amorphous film of a substituted Cu-phthalocyanine was investigated by time-resolved absorption spectroscopy by us¹⁰. It was revealed that the absorption spectrum at sub-nanosecond was quite similar to temperature difference spectrum of the ground state which was obtained by subtracting the high temperature spectrum from that of at 298 K. It was concluded that efficient photothermal conversion due to excitation-excitation annihilation occurs within 100 ps. We investigated systematically laser ablation mechanism of several polymer films with or without dopant by applying time-resolved spectroscopy^{3-7,13-16}.

Imaging of morphological dynamics :

Morphological changes and their dynamics are important in laser ablation phenomena in adding to the various photochemical and photophysical processes of excited molecules as mentioned above. Time-resolved imaging technique is powerful and useful for investigating the dynamics of morphological change. Until now several time-resolved imaging techniques such as time-resolved photography^{12,14}, time-resolved surface light scattering^{10,11}, optical microscopy¹⁵, and nanosecond time-resolved interferometry¹⁷ have been developed and applied to the laser ablation of polymer films. Srinivasan *et*

al. investigated the fragmentation dynamics of PMMA film by utilizing time-resolved photography¹². The first manifestation of the ablation is at 60 ns and is accompanied with a nearly transparent shock wave, while ejection of the fragmented materials began at a few hundreds ns after excitation. We developed nanosecond time-resolved interferometry which possess both the high vertical (20–30 nm) and the high temporal (10 ns) resolutions¹⁷. By using this nanosecond interferometry, systematic investigation of the etching dynamics of several polymers have been conducted^{13,17–26}. Moreover thanks to high spatial and high temporal resolutions of this method, it was revealed for the first time that some polymer films undergo transient expansion even below the ablation threshold and then contract to the original flat level without permanent morphological changes.

Our research purpose has been to clarify the dynamics and mechanisms underlying the laser-induced morphological changes of the polymer film, and we have devoted our efforts by utilizing nanosecond time-resolved interferometry, femtosecond and nanosecond time-resolved spectroscopy, and mass spectroscopy. In this account, we summarize our methodologies and results on laser ablation of polymer films and related phenomena by experimental data of morphological changes and dynamic spectroscopies and try to consider the dynamics and mechanism in terms of molecular and electronic levels.

Experimental

Femtosecond time-resolved absorption spectroscopy :

The system for femtosecond time-resolved absorption spectral measurement was reported elsewhere³⁸, which we explain here as a representative example. A fundamental beam of an amplified femtosecond Ti : sapphire laser (780 nm, 3–4 mJ/pulse, fwhm 170 fs) was frequency-doubled and used as a pump pulse. The residual fundamental beam after passing through an optical delay circuit was used for generating a femtosecond white continuum light. The continuum light was divided in two; one was used as a probe pulse for transient absorption measurement of samples and the other was for a reference in order to correct the shot-by-shot intensity fluctuation and spectral change of the white continuum light. Each transient spectrum was obtained usually by averaging 20 shots of the probe pulse.

Nanosecond time-resolved absorption spectroscopy :

The 2nd harmonic pulse (532 nm, 14 ns fwhm) of an output from a Q-switched Nd³⁺ : YAG laser (Continuum Surelite 1, 1064 nm) was used as an excitation nanosecond-light source. The output pulse of an OPO system (Continuum Surelite OPO) pumped with a 3rd harmonic pulse (355 nm, 8 ns fwhm) of a Q-switched Nd³⁺ : YAG laser (Continuum Surelite 2, 1064 nm) and the 3rd harmonic pulse itself were used as probe pulses. The probe pulse was divided into two by a quartz glass and was depolarized by a quartz plate; one pulse was introduced to a sample surface with a normal angle, while another was used as a reference. The intensity and temporal profiles of the two pulses were measured with two photodiodes (PD1 and PD2, Hamamatsu Photonics, S1722-02), respectively, and transient absorbance was calculated from these two signals. By changing the output wavelength from the OPO system and the delay time (Δt) between the excitation and the probe pulses, transient absorption spectra were examined. The delay time was controlled by a digital delay/pulse generator (Stanford Research System, DG 535) and monitored shot-by-shot with a digital oscilloscope. Output signal from a PD3 (Hamamatsu Photonics, S1722-02) detecting the excitation pulse was used as a trigger of the oscilloscope. Here $\Delta t = 0$ was defined as the time when the peaks of both excitation and probe pulses coincided with each other.

Transient absorbance measurement at the excitation wavelength :

Transient absorbance of the film at λ_{ex} was measured by using two photodiodes^{5–7}. A small part of the incoming laser pulse was separated by a quartz plate and detected by the first photodiode, while the transmitted laser pulse was simultaneously detected by the second photodiode. The signals from two photodiodes were recorded by a digital oscilloscope and then transient or time-integrated absorbance was calculated.

Etch depth measurement :

An excimer laser (Lambda Physik Lextra 200, KrF : 248 nm, 30 ns fwhm, XeF : 351 nm, 30 ns fwhm), or the tunable OPO system was used as an excitation light source for inducing the expansion/contraction and ablation. The fluence was adjusted by use of partially transmitting laser mirrors for excimer lasers and ND filters for OPO sys-

tem. A central area of the laser pattern was chosen with an appropriate aperture and then focused onto the sample surface by using a quartz lens ($f = 200$). Fresh surface of the sample film was chosen for all experiments. The depth profile was measured by a surface depth profiler (Sloan, Dektak 3), and the etch depth was obtained as a difference of averaged levels between non-irradiated and irradiated areas.

Nanosecond time-resolved interferometry :

To detect the laser-induced morphological change such as expansion/contraction and etching, nanosecond time-resolved interferometry, which was first developed by us in 1994¹⁷, was utilized. This system is in principle based on a Michelson-type interferometer and its schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 1. The excimer laser or the tunable OPO system was used as an excitation light source, while

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of ns time-resolved interferometry. Abbreviations are PD, photodiode; OS, oscilloscope; BS, beam splitter; PG, pulse generator; L, lens; M, mirror; ND, ND filter; AM, attenuator mirror; QG, quartz glass; BPF, band pass filter; BE, beam expander.

the 2nd harmonic pulse (532 nm, 14 fwhm) of the Q-switched Nd^{3+} : YAG laser (Continuum Surelite 1, 1064 nm) was used as a probe beam. The intensity of the excitation beam was adjusted by an attenuation mirror or a ND filter, and then the beam was focused onto the sample surface at a slightly tilted angle. The probe beam was divided into two by a beam splitter and these two beams were introduced separately to the sample surface and a quartz glass with a normal angle. By combining two beams reflected at the sample surface and the quartz glass, interference patterns were obtained and captured by a CCD camera (Sony, XC-77, 512×512 pixel). To remove the stray light, a band pass filter (Toshiba, G54, central wavelength : 540 nm) was set before the CCD camera. The

acquired interference pattern was stored in a personal computer and analyzed to estimate displacement of polymer surface. The delay time (Δt) was controlled by a digital delay/pulse generator (Stanford Research System, DG 535) and monitored shot-by-shot with a digital oscilloscope. Here $\Delta t = 0$ was defined as the time when both peaks of excitation and probe pulses coincided with each other at the polymer surface. In the experiment, a shift of one fringe spacing to the left or right corresponds to an expansion or etching of 266 nm, that is, a half wavelength of the probe laser, depending on optical condition.

Photoprimary processes under intense pulsed-laser irradiation

Polystyrene films doped with anthracene :

Polystyrene film doped with anthracene or anthracene- d_{10} were ablated by 351 nm laser irradiation in a high-vacuum apparatus, and velocity distribution of ejected species were measured with a quadrupole mass spectrometer³⁹. Repetitively irradiated surfaces were found to differ from fresh surfaces in giving different velocity distributions. Hence, only the velocity distributions of the ejected species from the fresh surfaces were analyzed in detail. When the etching of the surface took place at irradiation energy of several hundred mJ/cm^2 , the detected species were mainly anthracene and styrene monomers. Their distribution was analyzed by assuming a composite Maxwell-Boltzman (MB) distribution with high temperature (several hundred K) and low-temperature (250–300 K) MB components. It was suggested that photon energy absorbed by anthracene is converted into thermal energy via rapid internal conversion in a polystyrene matrix, resulting in thermal decomposition of the polymer matrix. Moreover it was pointed out that 30 photons should be absorbed to prepare a melt polymer at 995 K, which is the translational temperature of anthracene obtained in the mass spectrometry measurement.

It is interesting to understand how one anthracene molecule absorbs a few tens of photons during laser irradiation and why the photon energy is converted to heat without decomposing itself? To explain this finding we have proposed "cyclic multiphotonic absorption" process, as shown in Fig. 2. If a laser-absorbing molecule quickly

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the cyclic multiphotonic absorption mechanism. The symbol G, A, and A* represent the ground state of a dopant, transient states of a dopant, and their excited states, respectively.

relaxes to the state which can absorb photons again, the molecule would be excited repeatedly during the laser pulse and absorbed photon energy can be transferred to the surrounding molecules as an vibrational energy through the intermolecular energy transfer. As a result, the molecule would behave as a "molecular converter" of absorbed photon energy into the surrounding heat energy.

To confirm the cyclic multiphotonic absorption process, temporal profile of the dopant fluorescence was measured⁴ and compared to the computational results based on cyclic multiphotonic absorption in the ground state, the first excited state, or the lowest triplet state. It was revealed that the cyclic multiphotonic absorption mechanism through S_n-S_1 and T_m-T_1 relaxation well reproduced the fluorescence rise and decay curves upon the laser ablation of polystyrene doped with 0.1 M anthracene. Moreover calculated temperature based on the mechanism through T_m-T_1 transition agrees closely with the mean temperature of ejected anthracene and styrene obtained by mass spectroscopy. Thus we concluded that the cyclic multiphotonic absorption mechanism through T_m-T_1 relaxation is most probable in the anthracene-doped polystyrene film.

Poly(methyl methacrylate) film doped with aromatic molecules :

Laser ablation dynamics of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) film doped with pyrene, 5-diazo meldrum's acid, biphenyl, and *p*-terphenyl was investigated by applying nanosecond time-resolved spectroscopy⁵⁻⁷. We confirmed that the dopant molecule absorbs many photons during nanosecond laser irradiation above the ablation threshold without decomposing itself by directly monitoring the

transmitted excitation laser pulse. In the case of laser ablation of PMMA film doped with pyrene, it was considered that temperature elevation due to the photoabsorption facilitates the S_1-S_1 and T_1-T_1 annihilation and the recombination of the cation and electron or anion. In the case of PMMA film doped with 5-diazo meldrum's acid, the photodecomposition of the dopant has little or no effect on laser ablation, while temperature elevation through the cyclic multiphotonic absorption by the generated ketene eventually led to laser ablation. Moreover laser heating dynamics of PMMA film doped with biphenyl or *p*-terphenyl was studied quantitatively by the analysis of temperature-dependent T_1-T_1 annihilation, which is a result of the thermally-activated diffusion of the dopants. The comparison between observed T_1 decays and the simulated ones revealed the following; (1) most of the absorbed photon energy, at least 70%, is used to increase the temperature of the polymer matrix, (2) the cooling of the polymer matrix, mainly due to heat transfer into the quartz substrate, slows down the diffusion of the dopants and, accordingly, the T_1-T_1 annihilation, and (3) the temperature at the polymer-quartz interface after laser excitation remains almost constant up to at least a few microseconds.

Azobenzene substituted urethane-urea copolymer film :

First we summarize here photoprimary process of azobenzene substituted urethane-urea copolymer film studied by utilizing time-resolved spectroscopy¹⁶. Photochemical dynamics of the urethane-urea copolymer film upon femtosecond laser irradiation is considered. Transient absorption spectra were measured and are shown in Fig. 3 where λ_{ex} was 390 nm and fluence was 9.8 mJ/cm². Under this excitation condition, the sample film did not show any permanent morphological change after la-

Fig. 3. Transient absorption spectra of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film obtained by fs time-resolved absorption spectroscopy. Delay times are given in corresponding frames.

ser irradiation. In this experiment film thickness was 120 nm. A sharp negative peak was observed around 390 nm, which was ascribed to an artifact owing to a notch filter that blocks the scattering light of the excitation pulse. At the first stage broad positive and negative absorption bands were observed around 600 nm and 460 nm, respectively. The disappearance of the positive absorption band around 600 nm is followed by the appearance of a new positive absorption band around 400 nm and the red shift of the negative absorption. After a few ns the positive absorption around 600 nm almost disappeared, while the positive absorption around 400 nm and the negative absorption around 500 nm were still remained. These absorption changes completely disappeared after a few seconds.

The kinetics of the transient absorptions change at 400 nm and 600 nm, and the peak wavelength shift of the negative absorption were approximately represented by single-exponential functions and time constants are 8.1 ps, 7 ps, and 10 ps for the relaxation of positive absorption at 600 nm, the increase of positive absorption at 400 nm, and the red shift of negative absorption peak, respectively. It is worth noting that these time constants are same with each other. Furthermore according to previous other reports⁴⁰, owing to *trans-cis* photoisomerization of 4-dimethylamino-4'-nitroazobenzene (DANAB) in the polymer film the absorbance around 490 nm was decreased with the increase of concentration of the *cis* isomer, while absorbance around 400 nm was increased. This result resembles to the present spectral change observed at a few ns after excitation and chemical structure of DANAB is similar to azobenzene chromophore. Thus the positive and negative absorption at 0 ps are considered to correspond to generation of excited state of the *trans* isomer and depletion of ground state of *trans* isomer, respectively. Decay of the positive absorption around 600 nm and rise of the positive absorption around 400 nm correspond to relaxation of the excited *trans* isomer and generation of the *cis* one, respectively. The red shift of the negative absorption is due to concentration change of the excited *trans* and the *cis* isomers. Therefore it can be considered that the *cis* isomer of this sample possesses the broad absorption band around 400 nm. This result indicates that the excited *trans* form isomerizes to the *cis* one in a time scale of 10 ps in its polymer matrix.

Now we describe photochemical dynamics of the azobenzene chromophore investigated under intense nanosecond laser pulse irradiation. Transient absorption spec-

tra of the urethane-urea copolymer film under the nanosecond irradiation are shown in Fig. 4. Excitation wavelength and fluence were 532 nm and 35 mJ/cm², respectively. Under this excitation condition the sample film

Fig. 4. Transient absorption spectra of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film obtained at the fluence of 35 mJ/cm² for 532 nm excitation. The delay times are given in the corresponding frame.

did not show any permanent morphological change after laser irradiation. At 4 ns a small absorbance increase was observed at 355 nm and 420 nm, and bleaching was observed at wavelength longer than 430 nm. These absorbance change (Δ abs.) was gradually slowed down with time and at the late stage after a few min an original absorbance was recovered within the experimental error. It suggested that most of the azobenzene chromophore was not decomposed or not lost even after laser irradiation under this experimental condition. It is obvious that absorbance change at a few ns excited by the femtosecond and the nanosecond laser pulses are quite same. This result indicates that in the case of the intense nanosecond laser excitation the *trans-cis* photoisomerization is induced during excitation.

Fig. 5 shows transient absorbance change at 351 nm and 475 nm excitation, where the film thickness was 180 nm. In the case of 351 nm excitation, absorbance change was too small to detect, so a thicker film was used and the difference of the film thickness was corrected when analyzed. At the fluence less than 1 mJ/cm² the absorbance remained constant during laser irradiation at each λ_{ex} and its value is quiet similar to that obtained by the conventional spectrometer. This means that absorbance change was too small to detect or any appreciable reaction was not induced during excitation. In the case of 351

nm excitation, the absorbance gradually increased during laser irradiation at 100 mJ/cm². With increasing the fluence a similar but faster absorbance increase was observed. On the contrary, the absorbance decreased during excitation at 475 nm excitation, and with increase in the fluence the absorbance change gradually became large. The similar absorbance decrease was observed at 248 nm and 420~560 nm excitation, which was confirmed by systematic examination like Fig. 5.

absorbance did not change appreciably until 30 mJ/cm² and then it decreased with further increase in fluence.

Under the excitation condition where the absorbance changed during laser irradiation, it becomes possible that all molecules are excited, that is, one molecule absorbs several photons. To elucidate the role of transient species of the azobenzene chromophore in laser-induced morphological change, it is important to know how many

Fig. 5. Transient absorbance change (solid lines) of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film at excitation wavelength. Excitation wavelength and fluence are given in the corresponding frames. Dashed lines representing absorbance before excitation at the excitation wavelength are shown as a reference, while the temporal profile of each excitation pulse are given in the bottom.

Time-integrated absorbance at λ_{ex} was calculated for different fluence and also plotted in Fig. 5. The time-integrated absorbance induced upon excitation at far lower than the ablation threshold, near the threshold, and around 200 mJ/cm² were plotted in Fig. 5 with the temporal profile of respective excitation pulse. Here, the ablation threshold means the minimum fluence where permanent morphological changes was observed. At the fluence far lower than the ablation threshold, the time-integrated absorbance was same in principle to the conventional absorbance of the film. At 248 nm and 475~560 nm excitation, time-integrated absorbance was decreased at few mJ/cm² and with increase in fluence the decrease of absorbance change became large. On the other hand, at 351 nm excitation, time-integrated absorbance was increased a little with increase in laser fluence. It must be pointed out that, in the case of 420 nm excitation, time-integrated

photons of the excitation pulse were absorbed by one azobenzene chromophore. From the result of time-integrated absorbance, the averaged photon number absorbed by one azobenzene chromophore located between polymer surface and the penetration depth of the excitation pulse (d_{eff}) was estimated at the corresponding fluence. An azobenzene chromophore absorbed a few photons at the laser fluence above a few tens mJ/cm² for excitation with each λ_{ex} and the absorbed photon number increased with the fluence. Because the *cis* isomer is generated at a time scale of 10 ps, it can be considered that the *cis* isomer absorbs the photon and so the photon energy effectively converted to heat through *trans-cis-trans* photoisomerization and by cyclic multiphoton absorption by both the *trans* and the *cis* isomers. This explanation is schematically shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. The cyclic multiphotonic absorption mechanism in the azobenzene chromophore. Wave lines indicate intramolecular vibrational relaxation.

Nanometer-nanosecond expansion/contraction and etching dynamics

Surface morphological change dynamics below and/or above the ablation threshold of the several polymer films was examined by utilizing nanosecond time-resolved interferometry¹⁷⁻²⁵. Some representative examples of acquired time-resolved interference images are shown in Fig. 7. The fringe shift toward right side means expansion

under the experimental condition. Below the ablation threshold polymer film expanded just after excitation and then slowly contracted to the original thickness, while etching started just after excitation above the ablation threshold. Transient expansion and etching dynamics was obtained by analyzing the nanosecond time-resolved interferometric images.

Fig. 7. Nanosecond time-resolved interferometric images of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film at 351 nm excitation. Excitation fluence was (a) 70 mJ/cm² and (b) 160 mJ/cm². A fringe shift to the right represents an expansion. The delay times are given at the bottom of the images.

PMMA and poly(methyl acrylate) films doped with pyrene :

Expansion and contraction dynamics of PMMA and poly(methyl acrylate) (PMA) films doped with pyrene after 248 nm excitation was investigated¹⁸. At 150 mJ/cm², which is below the ablation threshold, polymer film of ~2 μm thickness showed a rapid expansion of about 250 nm and a following slow contraction, resulting in no permanent etching on the surface. To investigate the transient expansion dynamics we compared contraction behavior of irradiated PMMA films on two different kinds of substrates, quartz and undoped commercial PMMA plate. The expansion of the PMMA film on the quartz plate disappeared after 20 ms, while PMMA film on the undoped PMMA plate showed very slow contraction, that is, the expansion disappeared after a few seconds. This result indicated that contraction dynamics of the PMMA film affected by the substrate. Since the thermal diffusivity of a PMMA substrate is lower than that of quartz one, so that it is considered that the thermal process has a major role in the transient expansion of PMMA films upon excimer laser irradiation.

To confirm the photothermal mechanism, fluence dependence of the maximum expansion amplitude of PMMA and PMA films doped with 2 wt % pyrene was investigated and obtained result is plotted in Fig. 8. Around 65 mJ/cm², a knick point was observed for PMMA film and

Fig. 8. Fluence dependence of the maximum expansion of PMMA and PMA films below the ablation threshold (180 and 330 mJ/cm², respectively). Both films are doped with 2 wt % pyrene. Cited from H. Furutani, H. Fukumura and H. Masuhara, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, 100, 6871.

the slope increased by a factor of about 4.2, whereas the PMA film did not alter the slope. It is interesting that only PMMA film shows the discontinuous fluence dependence. Surface temperature of PMMA at the knick point was estimated to be about 410 K, which is a little higher than glass-rubber transition temperature (T_g) of PMMA; 378 K. Thermal expansion coefficient of the PMMA film increased when temperature exceeds T_g , while PMA is in the rubbery state at room temperature even before excitation. It was concluded that the discontinuous fluence dependence of the expansion amplitude is due to the glass-rubber phase transition of PMMA. Thus, we consider that the transient expansion and contraction dynamics of PMMA and PMA film can be explained well from the photothermal mechanism and glass-rubber phase transition.

Neat PMMA film :

The expansion/contraction and etching behavior of a neat PMMA film is induced by 248 nm excitation and directly measured by nanosecond interferometry¹⁹. Above the ablation threshold (1400 mJ/cm²), the film expands during excitation, and after 25% expansion of the thickness, we could not get a clear fringe pattern of the interference images of the irradiated area. This is because interference images became dark, which is eventually ascribed to ablated fragments. Below the threshold, the expansion rate is still high (a few nm/ns), and permanent swelling is observed after transient expansion and succeeding contraction. By decreasing the laser fluence below 800 mJ/cm², which is swelling threshold, permanent swelling was not observed, and at a few hundreds of mJ/cm², novel oscillatory expansion and contraction behavior was successfully demonstrated. The expansion amplitude as a function of laser fluence indicates that the polymer film undergoes phase transition from glass to rubber upon excitation with a fluence higher than 450 mJ/cm². In the glass state, the interpenetrating structure of the polymer film and associated free volume distribution may be changed upon irradiation, and photochemical degradation should be involved.

Neat polystyrene film :

We have directly measured molecular weight dependent surface morphological changes of neat polystyrene films after 248 nm excimer laser irradiation²⁰. In the case

of low molecular weights (3.0×10^3 and 5.0×10^3), the surface contracts exponentially. In the case of high molecular weight (1.0×10^6), however, two different contraction processes are observed, that is, a major contraction and a minor tail. The thermal diffusion coefficients of major components acquired experimentally from both high and low molecular weights are almost the same as the value in the literature, which indicates thermal diffusion is dominant for the major contraction. On the other hand the minor tail was observed only when the molecular weight is longer than characteristic length, so that it can be considered that the tail shows the effect of the entanglements.

Nitrocellulose film :

Laser-induced decomposition and accompanying ablation dynamics of a reactive nitrocellulose film was investigated by doping a Cu-phthalocyanine derivative as a light absorber²¹. While nitrocellulose does not absorb XeF 351 nm excimer laser pulse, the film heated instantaneously via rapid photothermal conversion in the doped Cu-phthalocyanine derivative. Below the ablation threshold, thermal expansion and contraction processes were directly followed in the nanosecond time region. Above the ablation threshold, the expansion of the film was started during the excimer laser irradiation, and then explosive decomposition was initiated, continuing in a few hundreds ns after the excitation. Temperature elevation caused by the excimer laser irradiation results in an exothermic decomposition of nitrocellulose, leading to a faster temperature rise of the film. Consequently self-acceleration of the reaction is enhanced and an explosive self-sustaining decomposition is induced after reaching the explosive decomposition condition.

Triazene polymer film :

The dynamic behavior of a photoetching process of a photosensitive triazeneopolymer film was studied during and after 351 nm laser irradiation¹³. At a fluence of 250 mJ/cm², a slight swelling of the film and darkening of the irradiated surface was initially observed, and then the etching process of the film was brought out around the peak time of the excitation laser pulse. The etching developed during laser irradiation and stopped almost at the end of the excimer laser pulse. On the other hand, at a

fluence of 60 mJ/cm², the etching started from nearly the end of the excimer laser pulse and the etching process continued until 140 ns. When the laser fluence is high enough, photodecomposition occurs densely leading to sudden ablation, so that thermal degradation cannot be observed. On the other hand, at 60 mJ/cm² the thermal process was successfully measured as photodecomposition is stopped. Since the decomposition of the triazeneopolymer is an exothermic reaction, it can be considered that photodecomposition of the polymer results in the temperature elevation, causing thermal degradation.

Polyurethane film :

A polyurethane sample film was prepared by adding phenol resin as a structural stabilizer and dynamics of laser-induced morphological change upon 248 nm excitation was investigated²². The ablation threshold by 248 nm excitation was determined to be 40 mJ/cm². Below the ablation threshold an expansion forms a bump and followed by rapid contraction, that is, expansion disappeared at about 1 μ s. Above the ablation threshold interferometric images were not disturbed by the decomposed products, which indicates that the film was decomposed efficiently into debris, fragments, aggregates, and so on and transient expansion was not observed. Moreover no appreciable debris was left. At the fluence of 310 mJ/cm², etching proceeds fast during the initial half of the excitation laser pulse, but stopped at the late stage of the pulse. The morphological behavior is quite different from that of photothermal expansion and contraction dynamics observed for PMMA, hence it is considered that laser ablation is induced photochemically.

Polyimide film :

Intense excimer laser excitation of polyimide film gives transient expansion and the following contraction, permanent swelling, and ablation, depending on excitation wavelength²³. Ablation by 248 nm excitation takes place only during the excitation laser pulse, and no debris was observed, while that by 351 nm excitation is brought about after sudden expansion. Permanent swelling was observed only for 351 nm excitation. Expansion and contraction dynamics at 351 nm excitation at low fluence is consistent with the simulation of temperature rise. This means that photothermal mechanism surely holds for this case. At 248 nm excitation, a hump in expansion and contrac-

tion profile becomes clear. We consider that the hump is not due to a photothermal origin. Since the 248 nm etching shows the strong photochemical nature, we consider that the rapid expansion and contraction observed in a few hundreds nanosecond is due to photochemical formation and recombination/leakage of decomposed small molecules. On the basis of the morphological dynamics, it is shown that photochemical and photothermal mechanisms can explain mostly the results obtained by 248 and 351 nm excitation, respectively.

Nanometer-nanosecond dynamics of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film

Photothermal transient expansion dynamics :

Nanosecond transient expansion, successive contraction, and etching dynamics of an azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film is summarized here^{3,16,24,25}. First, we investigated the time-resolved absorbance change at 540 nm and transient expansion dynamics under the same experimental condition. Fig. 9 shows the obtained

Fig. 9. Temporal profiles of nanosecond time-resolved transient absorption observed at 540 nm (O) and expansion/contraction dynamics (●) of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film. The solid and dashed curves represent the temporal profile of the excitation laser pulse and its time-integration, respectively.

results, where the film thickness was 330 nm, λ_{ex} was 532 nm, and fluence was 40 mJ/cm². As described above, it can be considered that the absorbance decrease shown in Fig. 9 represents generation of *cis* isomer due to photoisomerization and we have demonstrated that quick photoisomerization took place during laser irradiation. Therefore it was considered that the generated *cis* isomer can absorb the excitation photon and the photon energy is effectively converted to heat. We have reported that, when Cu-phthalocyanine solid is excited by an intense 170 fs laser pulse, an efficient photothermal conversion due to exciton-exciton annihilation occurs in the scale of 10 ps

after the excitation¹⁰. Moreover Dlott and co-workers reported that photon energy absorbed by doped molecule is converted to heat via vibrational cooling and heat up the polymer matrix in the 100 ps time scale with use of 100 ps pulse laser⁹. By considering that thermal equilibrium was achieved in the same time scale for our sample, it is reasonable to say that rise curve of absorbance change during laser pulse shown in Fig. 9 corresponds to increase in thermal energy and then polymer film underwent thermal expansion.

To clarify the photothermal process, fluence dependence of the expansion amplitudes at about 30 ns, where the amplitudes became maximum, are plotted for 351 nm, 532 nm, and 560 nm excitation in Fig. 10. It is worth noting that the expansion of the film does not show simple linear fluence dependence. The knick point was

Fig. 10. Fluence dependence of the expansion amplitude around 30 ns after the laser irradiation in azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer. Excitation wavelength is given in corresponding image. Cited from T. Tada, T. Asahi, M. Tsuchimori, O. Watanabe and H. Masuhara, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, 2004, 43, 5337.

observed around 45 mJ/cm², 23 mJ/cm², and 25 mJ/cm² for 351 nm, 532 nm, and 560 nm excitation, respectively, and the slope increased above this knick point. This result is quite similar to that of pyrene-doped PMMA and neat PMMA films. Therefore the present knick point of the urethane-urea copolymer and its slope changes are closely related to T_g and thermal expansion coefficient, respectively. The averaged temperature of the urethane-urea copolymer film at around 30 ns delay time was calculated from the simulation of one-dimensional heat conduction model described above. The temperatures at the knick points were 429 K, 445 K, and 434 K for 351 nm, 532 nm, and 560 nm excitation, respectively, and these values were slightly higher than T_g of the urethane-urea copolymer film; 413 K. Since the measured T_g was rather high when heating rate in experiment was increased⁴¹, it is reasonable to consider that the polymer was in the

prepared on a cold unexcited layer of the polymer film, can be heated up. So the maximum expansion amplitude at several λ_{ex} was examined from the viewpoint of the thickness of heated surface layer. From the interferometric measurement, the maximum expansion amplitude was estimated, while the averaged temperature and the thickness of heated surface layer was calculated from the simulation of one-dimensional heat conduction, where the absorption coefficient at the excitation fluence was calculated from time-integrated absorbance. The maximum expansion amplitude is plotted as a function of thickness of heated surface layer in Fig. 11. It is clear that the maximum amplitude increases linearly with the increase in the thickness of the heated surface layer, and the ratio of expansion to the thickness of the heated surface layer was 30% near the ablation threshold. This result also strongly confirms that the irradiated polymer film undergoes thermal expansion.

Fig. 11. (a) Schematic image of thickness of heated surface layer and expansion amplitude. (b) A relationship between expansion amplitude of azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film at around 30 ns after the laser irradiation and heat penetration depth.

rubber state above the knick point. Since it has been shown that thermal processes dominate transient expansion, the maximum expansion amplitude should be proportional to the thickness of the heated surface layer. By tuning λ_{ex} the surface layer with a variable thickness, which was

Cooling dynamics :

Next we consider the contraction dynamics of the film. The thermally swelled polymer film contracted in a few hundreds ns and μ s orders to the original flat level without a permanent morphological change below the abla-

tion threshold. It is expected that heat dissipation processes determine this contraction behavior. To clarify the relationship between contraction dynamics and heat dissipation processes, the dependence of contraction dynamics on λ_{ex} and film thickness was investigated. Tuning λ_{ex} eventually leads to heat up the surface layers with different thickness, and changing film thickness corresponds to vary the thickness of the cold layer beneath the heated surface layer. Here, the fluence of irradiated laser pulse at each λ_{ex} was set to be slightly lower than the ablation threshold.

When the film thickness was smaller than penetration depth of the excitation pulse (d_{eff}) or a little larger than d_{eff} , the heated films contracted in single exponential mode, which is called here as the single-exponential contraction. Here, d_{eff} was estimated from the time-integrated absorbance at the corresponding fluence. On the other hand, the contraction dynamics in which the film thickness was much larger than d_{eff} showed two components, which we call fast and slow components in double-expo-

nential contraction. These contraction dynamics of thin and thick film is roughly consistent with temperature lowering of the polymer film surface which was estimated from the simulation of one-dimensional heat conduction. Moreover, the relaxation time of the slow component in the double-exponential contraction and that of single one are estimated against the film thickness and the result can well fit to a following equation;

$$t \propto d^2,$$

where t and d denote the relaxation time and film thickness, respectively. The characteristic time for cooling by thermal diffusion over a certain distance obeys a similar equation^{42,43}. Thus, the result indicates that heat dissipation process is dominant both in the single-exponential contraction and in the slow component in double-exponential contraction. On the basis of these results, we considered that the fast and slow components in the double-exponential contraction of the thick film reflect the heat flux toward the quartz substrate and the heat dissipation

Fig. 12. Film thickness dependent heat dissipation processes. Excitation laser pulse was irradiated from the upside to the polymer film and the gray area means heated area due to laser irradiation.

process, respectively, while the single-contraction of the thin film reflects the heat dissipation process as shown in Fig. 12.

Laser ablation mechanisms :

λ_{ex} dependence of laser ablation dynamics of the urethane-urea copolymer film was investigated by utilizing etch depth and nanosecond time-resolved interferometric measurements. On the basis of the obtained results on the morphological changes and on photophysical processes of azobenzene chromophore, laser ablation mechanism was discussed in view of the penetration depth of the excitation pulse, photochemical and photothermal processes. Upon intense pulsed laser irradiation, permanent morphological changes of the sample film were observed at the laser intensities above a threshold. Etch depth at several λ_{ex} was examined against the laser fluence. When $\lambda_{\text{ex}} < 500$ nm, the laser-induced permanent swelling was not clearly observed and the etch depth increases monotonously with the laser fluence. On the other hand, at longer wavelength excitation ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \geq 500$ nm), the film first showed permanent swelling above a certain fluence and the maximum height of this morphological change increased with increasing λ_{ex} . A further increase in the fluence switched the irradiation effect on the surface from permanent swelling to etching, and the slope of the semi logarithm plot of the etch depth became steeper as λ_{ex} increases. Optical microscopic images of irradiated area show fibrous residues in the irradiated surface at longer wavelength excitation ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \geq 530$ nm). On the contrary, such residues were not clearly observed at shorter wavelength excitation. The ablation or swelling threshold (minimum fluence at which the permanent morphological changes were observed) at each λ_{ex} was determined and was plotted in Fig. 13(a). Hereafter, both values are simply called as the ablation threshold. Time-integrated absorbance near the ablation threshold is also plotted in Fig. 13(a). When the absorption coefficient was small, the ablation threshold was high, and vice versa. Permanent morphological changes induced by intense pulse laser irradiation clearly depended on λ_{ex} .

Absorbance, etch depth, and ablation threshold are key parameters to understand the laser ablation mechanism and are correlated with each other. Here on the basis of the experimental results and some assumptions, the relationship between these factors is discussed. According to Lambert's law the laser fluence (F_x) after pass-

ing through the layer of thickness x is given by

$$F_x = F_0 \exp(-\alpha x).$$

Here F_0 and α indicate the incident laser fluence and absorption coefficient, respectively. By assuming that Lambert's law holds under this experimental conditions and etching proceeds until a depth where the fluence of excitation pulse reduces to the etching threshold, the depth, d , is represented by the following simple equation³⁰ :

$$d = \alpha_{\text{eff}}^{-1} \ln (F_0/F_{\text{th}}).$$

α_{eff} was estimated from the result of etch depth measurement for all λ_{ex} and plotted in Fig. 13(b) with asterisk marker (*). The time-integrated absorbance at 200 mJ/cm², where the etching was induced, was also plotted in Fig. 13(b). It is worth noting that α_{eff} is not similar to the conventional absorption spectrum but quite close to the

Fig. 13. (a) Threshold of the film (O) and its time-integrated absorbance near the threshold (\blacktriangle) as a function of excitation wavelength. (b) Time-integrated absorbance at each excitation wavelength at 200 ~ 300 mJ/cm² (\square), and effective absorbance (*). The solid line is absorption spectrum obtained by conventional spectrometer. The sample is azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film.

time-integrated absorbance under the intense excitation condition. Obtained results are mostly explained by considering that penetration depth of the excitation pulse dominates etch depth.

Elucidation of the mechanism underlying laser-induced

morphological change has been done by analyzing dependence of etch depth on λ_{ex} and absorbance change at λ_{ex} . Complementally the etching dynamics was investigated by utilizing nanosecond time-resolved interferometry and by tuning λ_{ex} . Deformation of the fringe patterns can be recognized in the irradiated area just after laser irradiation and the temporal change of fringe pattern ceased completely, which indicates that etching process is finished. It must be pointed out that fringe pattern of irradiated area was always clearly observed during morphological change at 248 and 351 nm excitation. On the other hand, the fringe pattern at the irradiated area disappeared from a several ns to several μs at longer wavelength excitation ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \geq 420 \text{ nm}$). The duration of fringe loss at the irradiated area became long with increase in excitation wavelength and at 560 nm excitation the fringe pattern never came back again even after morphological change finished. By comparing the interference image with the depth profile, it becomes clear that the etched surface at 560 nm excitation become rough compared with that of 530 nm, so that fringe pattern did not come back again

important difference among fringe deformations at various λ_{ex} is the duration of fringe loss. To compare the etching dynamics, experimental condition and the time when the fringe pattern disappeared and came back again was listed in Table 1 with some spectroscopic and morphological data. In the case of UV excitation, fringe pattern at the irradiated area always clearly observed, which is similar to laser ablation of triazenopolymer and polyurethane, and nitrocellulose films. The result suggests that only gaseous products are generated and ejected by the excimer laser irradiation. In the case of 420 nm and 475 nm excitation, fringe pattern of the irradiated area disappeared until a few tens and a few hundreds ns after excitation, respectively. It is interesting to see why the vanished fringe pattern appeared again so quickly. It is usually considered that the fringe loss is mainly due to scattering of the probe pulse owing to the surface roughing of the polymer film and the ejection of fragmented debris. We have investigated the etching dynamics of several polymer films by utilizing nanosecond time-resolved interferometry and photography³⁻⁹. These results showed

Table 1. The time when the fringe patterns at the irradiated areas disappeared and appeared again. The sample is azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film. α_{eff} and absorbed energy density are defined in the text

Excitation wavelength (nm)	Case	Fluence (mJ/cm ²)	Time ^a (ns)	Time ^b (ns)	α_{eff} (μm^{-1})	Absorbed energy density (kJ/cm ³)	Etch depth (nm)
248	-	200	-	-	12.2	15.4	174
351	1	160	-	-	1.9	1.92	170
420	2	120	3	43	2.95	2.24	223
475	3	145	8.4	210	2.42	2.22	244
530	4	115	5	3000	2.56	1.86	110
	5	151	12	3000	2.21	2.11	212
560	6	160	5.4	*	1.8	1.82	297
	7	230	7	*	1.59	2.31	611

^aTime when the fringe patterns disappear.

^bTime when the fringe patterns appear again.

*The fringe patterns at the irradiated areas never come back again even after a few min.

after 560 nm pulse laser irradiation. It is quite interesting that duration of the fringe loss was closely depended on λ_{ex} , so that the duration was estimated at several excitation conditions and was summarized in Table 1.

On the basis of the behavior of fringe deformation, etching dynamics depending on λ_{ex} is discussed. Most

that ejected materials still remain at the front surface of the polymer film in the nanosecond time scale. So it is unreasonable to consider that the ejected materials is large enough to scatter the probe pulse and vanished from the front surface at the irradiated area in a nanosecond time scale. Therefore it is considered that the fringe loss ob-

served at 420 nm and 475 nm excitation is mainly due to the surface roughing of the polymer film. The fringe pattern was clearly observed even after the darkening, which indicates that debris or fragment of wavelength order was no longer ejected upon irradiation. This is consistent with the fact that no debris was observed around the etched pit. In the case of 530 nm and 560 nm excitation, the fringe loss continued for several μs and the fringe pattern never reappeared, respectively. These results are quite similar to laser ablation of the doped PMMA films. Thus obtained results suggest that not only surface roughing but also ejected large debris on the surface led to the scatter of the probe pulse. This consideration is supported by the fact that the fibrous residues were observed on the irradiated surface at 560 nm excitation.

As described above it has been pointed out that the etching dynamics and induced permanent morphological change depended on λ_{ex} , namely, the size of fragmented debris of shorter wavelength ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \leq 475 \text{ nm}$) excitation was smaller than that of longer one ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \geq 530 \text{ nm}$) and permanent swelling was observed at longer wavelength excitation. It is interesting and important to see why the etching dynamics and the permanent morphological change depended on λ_{ex} . First, decomposition dynamics of the polymer film is considered from the view point of absorbed energy density (see Table 1) which was stored within polymer film from surface to d_{eff} due to laser irradiation. The results of case 1, 4, and 6 in Table 1 show that almost same absorbed energy density is realized at each λ_{ex} . This means that shorter wavelength excitation leads to more effective decomposition of the polymer film. Same tendency was also observed among the results of case 2, 3, 5, and 7 in Table 1. Decomposition dynamics depending on λ_{ex} can not be well correlated to absorbed energy density. Consequently it is reasonable to consider that a single common underlying mechanism of laser ablation does not hold for the urethane-urea copolymer film, namely, the mechanism is changed from short to long wavelength excitation.

Next, decomposition dynamics of the polymer film is considered from the view point of photochemical processes. The result of the time-resolved absorption spectral measurement showed that the generation of the *cis* isomer leads to slight increase of absorbance at 420 nm, which suggests that the *cis* isomer possesses higher molar

absorptivity at 420 nm than the *trans* one, while the time-integrated absorbance at 420 nm excitation decreased, when the irradiated fluence exceeded 30 mJ/cm^2 . The observed absorbance decrease at 420 nm can not be interpreted in terms of the photoisomerization. Ronayette *et al.* studied the photoreduction of azobenzene in isopropanol and reported that only *cis* isomer was photoreducible⁴⁴. Watanabe *et al.* investigated photodegradation dynamics of an azobenzene-substituted polymer film and proposed two-step reaction⁴⁵. First step is a reversible photoisomerization reaction and second step is a successive irreversible reaction of the generated *cis* isomer. Many researchers reported that the irreversible photobleaching of the azobenzene chromophore was caused by reduction⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. Furthermore Vydra *et al.* found that excited azobenzene chromophore caused not only a destruction of itself but also a partial degradation of the polymer backbone by IR-spectroscopy and GPC measurements⁴⁷. Thus if we assume that the initial stage of photoreduction are common for our sample and azobenzene, photodegradation of our sample is induced through photoexcitation of the *cis* isomer. According to the result of our transient absorption spectral measurement, it is considered that the *cis* isomer of the sample possesses the broad absorption band around 400 nm and photodegradation is effectively induced by excitation at this band. Consequently, decrease of time-integrated absorbance at 420 nm excitation may be ascribed to photodegradation. It can be considered that at 420 nm and 475 nm excitation photodegradation of the azobenzene chromophore may be effectively induced compared with that of 530 nm and 560 nm excitation, and so fragmented debris becomes small. On the other hand, etching dynamics of polyurethane film at 248 nm excitation indicated that the film is decomposed efficiently into debris, fragments, and so on which are smaller than the wavelength of probe pulse as mentioned above. Thus it can be considered that, in the case of UV excitation, direct excitation of the main chain may become important. The most probable explanation of the obtained results is that owing to photodecomposition processes as described above fragmented debris generated at shorter wavelength excitation ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \leq 475 \text{ nm}$) becomes small compared with that of longer one ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} \geq 530 \text{ nm}$).

Finally, the permanent swelling dynamics of the polymer film is considered in terms of the penetration depth

of the excitation pulse, photochemical, and photothermal processes. As mentioned above we previously investigated the laser ablation dynamics of PMMA film doped with 5-diazo Meldrum's acid (DM)⁵. We considered that the permanent swelling is due to incomplete fragmentation and displacement of the deeper part of the film. Furthermore they calculated the amount of the photodecomposed DM, which corresponds to amount of generated N₂, and showed that photodecomposition of the dopant is not a main factor of the permanent swelling. This is because photothermal conversion by the photodecomposed transient species is very efficient. It was concluded that photothermal processes are dominant for inducing the permanent swelling even for polymer film containing photodecomposable dopant. In the case longer wavelength (500 ~ 560 nm) excitation, azobenzene chromophore may be stable during laser irradiation and so photon energy will be effectively converted to heat as mentioned above. Therefore it is reasonable to conclude that photothermal process was dominant and then permanent swelling was induced. Since time-integrated absorbance near the threshold was decreased with increasing λ_{ex} as shown in Fig. 13(a), it can be said that, due to the increase in the penetration depth of the excitation pulse, deeper part of the film contributes to the permanent swelling and the maximum height of this morphological change increased. These results were consistent with the our reported result⁴⁸. On the other hand, at shorter wavelength (248 ~ 475 nm) excitation, permanent swelling was not clearly observed. At this excitation wavelength range except for 248 nm, time-integrated absorbance near the ablation threshold was roughly same or lower than that at 500 nm excitation. Therefore this result also supports that a single common underlying mechanism of laser ablation does not hold for the urethane-urea copolymer film and photochemical processes played an important role in laser ablation at shorter wavelength excitation as considered above.

Summary

We have summarized the laser-induced ablation and expansion/contraction behavior of representative polymer films as nanometer-nanosecond dynamics. Nanometer surface displacement during and after excitation was observed directly with resolution of 12 nm and a few ns by utilizing our nanosecond interferometry. The transient

molecular species responsible to such morphological behavior were identified to be excited singlet and triplet states as well as radicals by time-resolved spectroscopy, which indicates that the dynamics and mechanism can be well interpreted in the framework of Jablonski diagram. The excited states and radicals absorb excitation photons during the excitation pulse width and convert excitation energy to vigorous lattice motion, leading to photothermal decomposition. As a result the transient expansion and permanent swelling are brought about. For triazeno polymer the interferometry gives clear image for whole delay time and expansion was not observed, which means that photochemical fragmentation occurs efficiently.

The more detailed examination was give for azobenzene-substituted urethane-urea copolymer film, where excited states of *trans* and *cis* forms of azobenzene have important roles in ablation.

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